

Multiphase Non-Isothermal Modeling of a Flowing Electrolyte - Direct Methanol Fuel Cell

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Abstract

Methanol crossover is one of the biggest shortcomings for direct methanol fuel cells (DMFCs) due to fact that it causes degradation to the cathode catalyst layer. The flowing electrolyte – direct methanol fuel cell (FE-DMFC) is a potential solution to this shortcoming, whereby the anode and cathode are separated by a flowing liquid electrolyte, such as diluted sulfuric acid. Any methanol that attempts to crossover is removed by the flowing electrolyte channel, thus protecting the cathode. Many researchers have modeled this fuel cell, however the majority of these studies have been single phase and examined the performance of the FE-DMFC under different operating conditions. Recently, a two-phase model of the FE-DMFC has been developed using a single-domain formulation of the multiphase mixture model (MMM). Due to the more realistic modeling predictions from this multiphase model, the single domain formulation will be extended to account for 2D and non-isothermal effects within the FE-DMFC. This proposed two-dimensional two phase, non-isothermal model is formulated and solved in a COMSOL Multiphysics environment and validated against experimental FE-DMFC data. The physics of this fuel cell are examined and discussed for varied inlet temperatures and flow rates of the anode, cathode and flowing electrolyte channel as well as varied set point temperatures (channel wall temperatures). A focus is placed on the energy and thermo-osmotic transport within the fuel cell and their effect on the fuel cell's performance.

Keywords: DMFC, Comsol Multiphysics, non-isothermal, simulation, two phase

I. Introduction

The direct methanol fuel cell (DMFC) is an electrochemical device that produces electricity from methanol (the fuel) and an oxidant such as air. This fuel cell type is a promising candidate for portable applications due to the fact that its fuel is in the liquid state at room temperature, allowing for an energy dense and inexpensive fuel that can easily be stored (Colpan et al., 2008; Wang et al., 2008). Figure 1 displays a schematic of this fuel cell.

In this diagram, it can be seen that this fuel cell is composed of several layers. From left to right, these layers include: the anode fuel channel (AFC), anode backing layer (ABL), anode catalyst layer (ACL), membrane (M), cathode catalyst layer (CCL), cathode backing layer (CBL) and cathode air channel (CAC). The operation principle of the DMFC is as follows: diluted methanol is supplied at the AFC inlet and is transported through the ABL (e.g. carbon cloth or carbon paper) to the ACL (e.g. Pt-Ru/C), where it reacts with the catalyst to produce electrons, protons and carbon dioxide, following the reaction shown in Equation 1. The protons conduct through the membrane (e.g. Nafion[®]) to the CCL, whereas the electrons conduct through the ABL, external load, CBL and reach the CCL (e.g. Pt/C). In the cathode, oxygen is supplied at the CAC inlet and is transported through the air channel and CBL (e.g. carbon cloth or carbon paper). The protons and electrons, which were supplied from the anode reaction, react with the supplied oxygen in the CCL, following the reaction

shown in Equation 2. In addition to this reaction, unreacted methanol can cross through the membrane and react within the CCL, following the reaction shown in Equation 3.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the DMFC

One of the main shortcomings of the DMFC is the performance degradation caused by methanol crossover, which gives rise to a reduction in fuel cell's power density and electrical efficiency. To circumvent

this issue, Kordesch proposed the flowing electrolyte concept, whereby the anode and cathode are separated by a flowing liquid electrolyte, such as diluted sulfuric acid. A schematic of this fuel cell is shown in Figure 2, and this fuel cell is known as the flowing electrolyte – direct methanol fuel cell, or FE-DMFC. This fuel cell design is intended to remove any methanol which attempts to crossover, thus potentially allowing this new fuel cell to perform like a DMFC without the effects of methanol crossover in the cathode (Kordesch et al., 2001). Various single phase studies and models have been developing about the FE-DMFC by researchers. Kjeang et al. (2005, 2006) studied the methanol crossover reduction in the flowing electrolyte channel with different operating parameters, through three dimensional (3D) modeling. Colpan et al. (2011, 2012) developed a 1D and 2D model of the FE-DMFC, to predict the performance of the fuel cell under different operating conditions and fuel, air, and FEC inlet velocities. Ouellette et al. (2015) extended Colpan's a one-dimensional FE-DMFC model to predict how the performance of the changes the inlet concentration of the FE, as well as the flow rate and thickness of the flowing electrolyte channel (FEC). The performance of a single cell FE-DMFC was experimentally studied and compared to a regular DMFC by Sabet-Sharghi et al. (2013). The flowing electrolyte layer was modelled, by Duivesteyn et al. (2013, 2013), as a porous domain in ANSYS CFX. General flow behaviour and the effects of volume flux, temperature, channel thickness, and porous material properties are investigated. Kablou et al. (2015) experimentally and numerically studied the stack level FE-DMFC.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the FE-DMFC

Another key problem in DMFCs, is the two phase flow within the anode and cathode, and has been shown to be an important feature to include in fuel cells. There are two approaches that are extensively used in literature, the multi-fluid model (MFM) (Rice and Faghri 2006; Sun et al., 2005; Xu et al., 2008) and the multiphase mixture model (MMM) (Jung 2013; F. Liu and Wang 2007; W. Liu and Wang 2007; Z. H. Wang and Wang 2003). Ouellette et al. (2015a, 2015b) improved up the MMM approach by developing a new single domain FE-DMFC model.

The thermal management is also another important

issue to consider in fuel cell design, as this affects the durability of the MEA as well as the transport of species and thus kinetics within the fuel cell (Djilali 2007; Siegel 2008; Wang et al. 2011). Although there are several published studies concerning non-isothermal two phase DMFCs, this type of analysis has not been conducted on the FE-DMFC.

Therefore, to further understand the FE-DMFC's performance, Ouellette et al.'s (2015) MMM model is extended to account for multidimensional and non-isothermal effects. A series of parametric studies were conducted with this new model to understand how the inlet temperatures of the anode and cathode affect the temperature distribution and species transport within the fuel cell. These findings are used to provide recommendations on operating procedures to enhance the fuel cell's performance.

II. Numerical scheme

In this model, the conservation equations (mass, momentum, chemical species, charge, and energy) and other auxiliary equations (e.g. Butler-Volmer equation) are coupled together and solved using COMSOL Multiphysics, which is a commercial software package based on finite element analysis. The main assumptions within this model are as follows.

- The fuel cell operates under steady state conditions.
- Methanol is fully consumed at the CCL-CBL interface.
- The inlet FEC velocity profile is uniform
- The BLs and CLs have the same porous properties.
- All fluids are ideal and exist in equilibrium.

As can be seen below, mass (Eq. (4)), momentum (Eq. (5)), species (Eq. (6)), energy (Eq. (7)) and charge (Eqs. (8) and (9)) are presented in concise form as follows:

$$\nabla \cdot (\rho u) = \left(\sum M^k S_{gen}^k \right) - \left(\sum M^k (\nabla \cdot N_e^k) \right) \Big|_{CL} = S_{gen} + S_{trans} \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\rho}{\varepsilon_p} \left((u \cdot \nabla) \frac{u}{\varepsilon_p} \right) = \nabla \cdot \left[-PI + \frac{\mu}{\varepsilon_p} (\nabla u + (\nabla u)^T) - \frac{2\mu}{\varepsilon_p} (\nabla \cdot u) I \right] - \left(\mu K^{-1} + \beta_F |u| + \frac{Q_{br}}{\varepsilon_p} \right) u + F \quad (5)$$

$$\nabla \left[-D_{lg}^k \nabla C_i^k + u_{lg}^k C_i^k \right] = S_{gen}^k + S_{gen}^{trans} \quad (6)$$

$$\nabla \left(-k_{eff} (\nabla T) + \gamma_T c_{p,eff} \rho u T \right) = S_{gen}^T \quad (7)$$

$$0 = \nabla \cdot (\sigma_l \nabla \phi_l) + S_{c,l} \quad (8)$$

$$0 = \nabla \cdot (\sigma_s \nabla \phi_s) + S_{c,s} \quad (9)$$

In order to find the mixture velocity (u) and pressure distribution, equations (4) and (5) are directly coupled together. This velocity is subsequently used to calculate the convective mode of transport within Eqs. (6) and (7). The concentration profile of each species (methanol, water, oxygen) is obtained from Eq. (6), where as the temperature profile is obtained from Eq. (7) and the current distributions are obtained from Eqs. (8) and (9).

In this study, the temperature distribution is now accounted for. Therefore, the equilibrium phase concentrations now become sole functions of temperature, giving rise to a thermo-osmotic flux. In the case of the water species transport equation, Eq. (6), the mixture water concentration is tracked, and the thermo-osmotic flux is treated as a transport source term. The final form of the water transport equation is shown below.

$$\begin{aligned} & \nabla \cdot \left[-D_{lg}^{H_2O} \nabla C^{H_2O} + u_{lg}^{H_2O} C^{H_2O} \right] \\ & = S_{gen}^{H_2O} - \nabla \cdot \left[-D_{lg}^T (\nabla T) + \varepsilon_e n_d^{H_2O} \frac{i}{F} \right] = S_{gen,eff}^{H_2O} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The corresponding thermo-osmotic diffusion coefficient is shown below for the case where the electrolyte, gas and liquid phases all co-exist.

$$\begin{aligned} D_{lg}^T = & -D_l^{H_2O} \frac{dC_l^{H_2O}}{dT} - D_g^{H_2O} \frac{dC_g^{H_2O}}{dT} - D_e^{H_2O} \frac{dC_e^{H_2O}}{dT} \frac{d\lambda_{wc}}{dT} \\ & - \frac{\lambda(1-\lambda)K}{v} \left(\frac{C_l^{H_2O}}{\rho_l} - \frac{C_g^{H_2O}}{\rho_g} \right) \frac{dP_c}{dT} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

For the methanol transport equation, the thermo-osmotic flux can be treated as a convective term, as shown in Table 1. No changes are necessary for the oxygen concentration profile.

The fuel cell geometry, the two-phase diffusion coefficient, D_{lg}^k , and velocity, u_{lg}^k , for each species, boundary conditions used within model, electrochemical and transport properties, as well as source/sink terms of each species, S_{gen}^k , S_T , $S_{c,l}$, $S_{c,s}$ are shown in Table 1-7, respectively.

The energy released or absorbed through phase change, is typically accounted for in the energy equation (Eq. (7)) through a source term, shown below.

$$m_{fg} h_{fg} = \nabla \cdot (h_{fg}^o \rho_l u) \quad (12)$$

However, this form of the source term was found to cause the presented model to be unstable. Therefore, the phase change process is approximated as the phase change between gaseous and liquid water. This allows for the following form of the phase change process, which can be treated as an effective thermal

conductivity.

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left[\left(k_{gd}^{eff} + M^{H_2O} D_g^{H_2O} \frac{dC_{sat}^{H_2O}}{T} \right) \frac{dT}{T} \right] = \frac{d}{dx} \left(k_{eff} \frac{dT}{x} \right) \quad (13)$$

$$k_{fg} = h_{fg}^o M^{H_2O} D_g^{H_2O} \frac{dC_{sat}^{H_2O}}{T} \quad (14)$$

II.1. Numerical procedure

The conservation equations (Eqs. 4-9) are solved using COMSOL Multiphysics 5, which is based on finite element methods. In order to solve the equations of the, the following built-in modules were used:

- The Transport of Diluted Species in Porous Media interface to solve the oxygen, water and methanol concentration fields.
- The Secondary Current Distribution interface to solve the charge transport equations.
- The Free and Porous Media Flow interface to solve the Navier-Stokes and continuity equations.
- The Heat Transfer in Porous Media interface to define temperature field in fuel cell.

In order to build mesh, the maximum element size was set to 10^{-6} m and the maximum element grow rate was set to 1.1. Grid independence was achieved with approximately 220000 elements. Due to the nonlinearity of the equations, the stationary nonlinear setting was used and each governing equation was solved sequentially each using a direct solver, specifically MUMPS (multifrontal massively parallel sparse direct solver).

Table 1. Fuel cell geometry

Parameter	Value	Units
Cell Length	50×10^{-3}	m
Active Area	2.5×10^{-3}	m ²
Thickness		
ABL and CBL	0.24×10^{-3}	m
AFC and CAC	1.5×10^{-3}	m
AM and CM	0.183×10^{-3}	m
FEC	0.610×10^{-3}	m
ACL and CCL	28×10^{-6}	m
Channel Dimensions		
Width	1.5×10^{-3}	m
Depth	1.5×10^{-3}	m

Table 2. Two phase diffusion coefficient and velocity

Species	D_{lg}^k	u_{lg}^k
Methanol	$D_l^{MeOH} + \frac{D_g^{MeOH}}{k_H^{MeOH}} + D_e^{MeOH}$	$\gamma^{MeOH} u \left(s + \frac{1-s}{k_H^{MeOH}} \right) + j_l \left(\frac{1}{\rho_l} - \frac{1}{k_H^{MeOH} \rho_l} \right) + \left(\varepsilon_e \frac{n_d^{H_2O}}{C_l^{H_2O}} \frac{i}{F} \right) - \left(D_g^{MeOH} \frac{\partial(1/k_H^{MeOH})}{\partial T} \right) \nabla T$
Oxygen	$D_g^{O_2}$	$\gamma^{O_2} u (1-s) - \frac{j_l}{\rho_g}$
Water	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} D_g^{H_2O} + D_{\lambda,eff}^{H_2O} \dots C^{H_2O} \leq C_{g,sat}^{H_2O} \\ D_{cap}^{H_2O} + D_{\lambda,eff}^{H_2O} \dots C^{H_2O} \leq C^{H_2O} \leq C_l^{H_2O} \\ D_l^{H_2O} + D_{\lambda,eff}^{H_2O} \dots C^{H_2O} = C_l^{H_2O} \end{array} \right.$	$\gamma^{H_2O} u$

Table 3 – Boundary conditions used within the model.

Boundary condition	Location	Symbol	Value	Units
Molar concentration MeoH	AFC-ABL	$C_{FC,in}^{MeoH}$	4000	mol m ⁻³
		$C_{CCL CBL}^{MeoH}$	0	mol m ⁻³
O ₂	CBL-AC	$C_{FC,in}^{O_2}$	$x_{O_2} \frac{P_{ac,in}}{RT}$	mol m ⁻³
H ₂ O	AFC-ABL	$C_{AFC ABL}^{H_2O}$	$(s_a C_l^{H_2O}) + (s_a C_g^{H_2O})$	mol m ⁻³
	CAC-CBL	$C_{CAC CBL}^{H_2O}$	$(s_c C_l^{H_2O}) + (s_c C_g^{H_2O})$	mol m ⁻³
Temperature	AFC Inlet	T	80	°C
	CAC Inlet	T	80	°C
	FEC Inlet	T	80	°C
	AFC and CAC Wall	T	80	°C
Electrode potential phase	FC-ABL	$\phi_{s,FC ABL}$	0	V
	ABL-AC	$\phi_{s,CBL AC}$	V_{cell}	V
Inlet velocities	AFC Inlet	$u_{FC,in}$	$\frac{\xi_a i_{ref} A}{6FC_{FC,in}^{MeOH} A_{channel}}$	m s ⁻¹
	CAC Inlet	$u_{AC,in}$	$\frac{\xi_c i_{ref} A}{4FC_{FC,in}^{O_2} A_{channel}}$	m s ⁻¹
	FEC Inlet	$u_{FEC,in}$	$\frac{Q_{FEC}}{w_{cell} t_{FEC}}$	m s ⁻¹
Outlet pressures	Anode	$P_{a,out}$	1	atm
	Cathode	$P_{c,out}$	1	atm
	FEC	$P_{FEC,out}$	1	atm

Table 4. Summary of source terms.

Source/ Sink Terms	Expression						
	ABL	ACL	AM	FEC	CM	CCL	CBL
S_{gen}^{MEOH}	0	$-\frac{j}{6F}$	0	0	0	0	0
$S_{gen}^{O_2}$	0	0	0	0	0	$-\frac{j}{4F} - 2\frac{j_{xover}}{6F}$	0
$S_{gen}^{H_2O}$	0	$-\frac{j}{6F}$ $-\nabla\left(\varepsilon_{e,ACL}n_d^{H_2O}\frac{i}{F}\right)$	$-\nabla\left(n_d^{H_2O}\frac{i}{F}\right)$	$-\nabla\left(n_d^{H_2O}\frac{i}{F}\right)$	$-\nabla\left(n_d^{H_2O}\frac{i}{F}\right)$	$\frac{j}{2F} + 2\frac{j_{xover}}{6F}$ $-\nabla\left(\varepsilon_{e,CCL}n_d^{H_2O}\frac{i}{F}\right)$	0
$S_{gen}^{CO_2}$	0	$\frac{j}{6F}$	0	0	0	$\frac{j_{xover}}{6F}$	0
S_{gen}^T	$\frac{(i_s)^2}{\sigma_s}$	$\frac{(i_e)^2}{\sigma_e} + \frac{(i_s)^2}{\sigma_s}$ $+ j_a\left(\left \eta_a\right - \frac{T\Delta S_{MOR}}{6F}\right)$	$\frac{(i_e)^2}{\sigma_e}$	$\frac{(i_e)^2}{\sigma_e}$	$\frac{(i_e)^2}{\sigma_e}$	$\frac{(i_e)^2}{\sigma_e} + \frac{(i_s)^2}{\sigma_s} +$ $+ j_c\left(\left \eta_c\right - \frac{T\Delta S_{OOR}}{4F}\right)$ $- j_{xover}\frac{T\Delta S_{MOR}}{6F}$	$\frac{(i_s)^2}{\sigma_s}$
S_{trans}	CLs						
	$\nabla \cdot \left[D_{\lambda,eff}^{H_2O} M^{H_2O} (\nabla C^{H_2O}) + D_e^{MeOH} M^{MeOH} (\nabla C_l^{MeOH}) - M^{MeOH} \nabla \cdot \left(\varepsilon_e \frac{n_d^{MeOH}}{C_l^{MeOH}} \frac{i}{F} \right) C_l^{MeOH} \right]$ $- M^{H_2O} \nabla \cdot \left(\varepsilon_e \frac{n_d^{H_2O}}{C_l^{H_2O}} \frac{i}{F} \right) C_l^{H_2O} + \left(M^{H_2O} D_e^{H_2O} \frac{dC_e^{H_2O}}{d\lambda_{wc}} \frac{d\lambda_{wc}}{dT} \right) \cdot (\nabla T)$						

Table 5. Electrochemical and transport properties used in modeling study

Parameter	Symbol	Expression	Units
Proton conductivity			
AM and CM	K_{AM} and K_{CM}	$(0.5139\lambda_{wc} + 0.326)\exp\left[-1268\left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{303.15}\right)\right]$	S m ⁻¹
FEC	K_{FEC}	$(-1.26 \times 10^{-3})T^2 + (1.05032)T - 173.164$	S m ⁻¹
Thermal conductivity			
Water liquid phase	k_{liquid}	$(-1.118 \times 10^{-5})T^2 + (8.388 \times 10^{-3})T - 0.9004$	W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
Water gas phase	k_{gas}	$(-1.118 \times 10^{-4})T - (2.404 \times 10^{-2})$	W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
Effective thermal conductivity	k_{eff}	$\varepsilon s k_l + \varepsilon(1-s)k_g + (1-\varepsilon-\varepsilon_e)k_s + \varepsilon_e k_e + k_{fg}$	W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
Heat capacitance			
Liquid phase of water	$C_{p,liq}$	4078.38	J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
Gas phase of water	$C_{p,gas}$	$(-4.281 \times 10^{-6})T^2 + (1.371 \times 10^{-2})T + 25.431$	J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
Electrolyte phase	$C_{p,mem}$	1090	J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
Effective heat capacitance	$C_{p,eff}$	$sc_{p,l} + (1-s)c_{p,g}$	J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹

Table 6. Fuel cell dimensions and material properties used in modeling study

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Units
Contact angle			
ABL and CBL	$\theta_{c,ABL}$ ve $\theta_{c,CBL}$	110	degrees
ACL and CCL	$\theta_{c,ACL}$ ve $\theta_{c,CCL}$	110	degrees
AM and CM	$\theta_{c,AM}$ ve $\theta_{c,CM}$	90.01	degrees
FEC	$\theta_{c,FEC}$	110	degrees
Thermal Conductivity			
AFC and CAC	k_{AFC} and k_{CAC}	20	W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
ABL and CBL	k_{ABL} and k_{CBL}	3	W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
ACL, CCL and FEC	k_{ACL} and k_{CCL}	3	W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
AM and CM	k_{AM} and k_{CM}	0.25	W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹

Table 7. Constitutive electrochemical equations.

Constitutive equations	
Anodic Non-Tafel expression	$j_a = \frac{i_{oa,ref} C^{MeOH} \exp\left(\frac{\alpha_a F}{RT} \eta_a\right)}{\left(\left(C^{MeOH} + K_a \exp\left(\frac{\alpha_a F}{RT} \eta_a\right)\right) * t_{ACL}\right)}$
Cathodic Tafel expression	$j_c + j_{xover} = \frac{i_{oc,ref} (1-s) \frac{C^{O_2}}{C_{ref}^{O_2}} \exp\left(\frac{\alpha_c F}{RT} \eta_c\right)}{t_{CCL}}$
Anodic overpotential	$\eta_a = \phi_s - \phi_l - E_a^{Eq}$
Cathodic overpotential	$\eta_c = -(\phi_s - \phi_l - E_c^{Eq})$
Crossover current density	$j_{xover} = \frac{i_{oa,ref} C^{MeOH} \exp\left(\frac{\alpha_a F}{RT} \eta_c\right)}{\left(\left(C^{MeOH} + K_a \exp\left(\frac{\alpha_a F}{RT} \eta_c\right)\right) * t_{ACL}\right)}$

III. Results and discussions

III.1. Baseline condition

The methanol concentration, oxygen concentration, liquid saturation and temperature distributions are shown in Fig. 3, for a cell voltage of 0.4 V ($i = 1360.4 \text{ A m}^{-2}$) cell voltage. In Fig. 3a, the methanol concentration decreases along the length-wise (y -direction) and thickness-wise (x -direction) directions due to the increased consumption of methanol within ACL. In the ACL the production of protons gives rise to the electro-osmotic drag of methanol through the membrane. In the FEC, the methanol concentration significantly decreases due to the convective crossflow, reducing the crossover current density to negligible levels, with a maximum of $\sim 400 \text{ A m}^{-2}$ at 0.9 V.

The oxygen distribution at a cell voltage of 0.4 V is shown in Fig. 3b. The concentration distribution is shown at the top, bottom and middle of the fuel cell is shown in Fig. 4, for a cell voltage of 0.9 V, 0.6 V, and 0.3 V. As can be seen in these figures, the oxygen concentration primarily decreases along the thickness-wise direction. Although the oxygen concentration also decreases in the length-wise direction, its decrease is very small in comparison to the thickness-wise decrease due to the much higher velocity in the length-wise direction, allowing for a low residence time within the CAC. The decrease in oxygen concentration within the CBL and CCL is primarily attributed to the higher mass transport resistance within these porous layers, in comparison to the CAC, as well as the consumption of oxygen within the CCL. However, the decrease in concentration in the thickness-wise direction is still quite small due to oxygen's high molecular diffusivity.

The liquid saturation distribution within the whole single cell is shown Fig. 3c and the distributions along the thickness-wise direction for the top, bottom and middle of the fuel cell at different cell voltages (0.3, 0.6 and 0.9 V) is shown in Fig. 5. As shown in both

figures, the liquid saturation profile within the anode and FEC are very high, ~ 0.9 , and constant for the whole range of cell voltages. As the cell voltage decreases, the liquid saturation within the ACL decreases due to the consumption of methanol and water, and the production of carbon dioxide. At the lowest cell voltage, 0.3 V, the liquid saturation decreases to a value of 0.89 (a 1% decrease). The cathode also showed the same type of trend. However, in this case, the liquid saturation profile increased from a value of 0.1 to 0.11 at a cell voltage of 0.3 V. This increase in liquid saturation is due to the combination of water crossover from the FEC to the cathode and due to the generation of water from the ORR and MOR from any crossed over methanol. The liquid saturation within the FEC also, negligibly changes due to the lack of chemical reactions within this layer.

(a) Methanol (b) Oxygen (c) Saturation (d) Temperature
Figure.3 Distribution of methanol concentration (a), oxygen concentration (b), saturation (c) and temperature (d) at a cell voltage of 0.4 V ($i = 1360.4 \text{ A m}^{-2}$) at 80 °C cell temperature.

Figure 4. Concentration of oxygen at the bottom, mid, and top of the cell with different cell voltages.

Figure 5. Liquid saturation-wise distribution of mid of the whole cell.

The temperature distributions are shown in Fig. 3d and the distributions along the thickness-wise direction for the top, bottom and middle of the fuel cell at different cell voltages (0.3, 0.6 and 0.9 V) is shown in Fig. 6. As can be seen in these figures, the CCL is the warmest layer due to the heat generated by Ohmic heating as well as the electrochemical reactions. The highest temperature difference achieved within this fuel cell was $\sim 3.5^\circ\text{C}$ at a cell voltage of 0.3 V. The next warmest location was within the ACL, for the same reasoning; where the highest temperature difference was $\sim 2.8^\circ\text{C}$ at a cell voltage of 0.3 V. Although the FEC does cool the fuel cell, especially near the anode and cathode outlets, the fuel cell acts as a crossflow heat exchanger, where the warmest section of the fuel cell was found to be near the midpoint of the channel length.

Figure 6. Temperature difference of the mid of the cell

III.2. Effect of Anode Inlet Temperature

When the inlet temperature of the anode was varied from 20°C to 80°C in 20°C steps, it was found that there was a small thermal entrance length (~ 0.8 cm) for the coldest temperature; see Fig. 7. It was found that this was primarily due to the fact that for a given flow rate or stoichiometry, the velocity of methanol is rather low in comparison to air. This allowed for increased heat transfer from the remainder of the fuel cell to the AFC. Even for a flow velocity that is set 10 times higher than the base line value, the maximum cell temperature only decreased by 1°C .

Figure 7. Temperature distribution of at the mid of the AFC along the length (y) direction at 0.3 V with different fuel temperature

Near the anode entrance however, anode temperature caused the CCL to cool by $\sim 3^\circ\text{C}$ at a cell voltage of 0.9 V and $\sim 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ at cell voltage of 0.3 V, as shown in Fig. 8. This difference in temperature caused gaseous water to migrate to this colder zone, where it condensed. This process is known as the heat pipe effect. However, once the AFC thermally equilibrated itself with its surroundings, further along the channel, evaporation occurred within the CCL. This behavior suggests that local flooding within the CCL is possible if 20°C methanol is supplied while the fuel cell is set to operate at a temperature of 80°C .

Figure 8. Temperature difference of the bottom of the cell at 0.3 V with different inlet AFC temperature.

III.3. Effect of Cathode Inlet Temperature

When the cathode's inlet temperature is varied, it was found that unlike the anode, the air's thermal entrance length was much larger than that of the anode's. In the tested cases, the 40°C and 60°C inlet temperature cases did not reach the cell temperature by the cathode exit, due to the high cathode velocity. This can be seen in Fig. 9.

Figure 9. Temperature distribution of at the mid of the CAC along the length (y) direction at 0.3 V with different air temperatures.

When comparing the fuel cell's temperature distribution, when the cathode's inlet temperature is varied, it was found that this parameter influenced the overall temperature more significantly than that of the anode inlet temperature. This is primarily attributed to the air's low thermal conductivity and high velocity. This in turn resulted in a low residence time which would allow for less heat to be transferred to the fluid within the CAC. Furthermore, since the air's velocity and molecular diffusivity are both high, this allowed for a high degree of convective cooling to the rest of the fuel cell. This can be seen by the midplane temperature profile of the fuel cell in Fig. 10. Furthermore, it can be seen in this figure that at the lowest inlet CAC temperature, this caused the mid-plane temperature to be ~10°C lower than that of the set point temperature. This caused a flooding condition within the CAC, driven by the heat pipe effect. As such, it is recommended to maintain comparable inlet temperatures to those of the set point temperature of fuel cell, to prevent flooding within the cathode.

Figure 10. Temperature difference of the bottom of the cell at 0.3 V with different inlet CAC temperatures.

IV. Conclusions

A nonisothermal, multi-phase 2D model of a FE-MDFC has been developed to explain the interactions between two-phase transfer and phase change heat transfer. In order to develop this model, the commercial software, Comsol Multiphysics 5.0, was used to solve the governing conservation equations of momentum, mass, species, charge, and energy numerically. After then, the temperature, liquid saturation, concentration of the methanol and oxygen distribution were examined at baseline condition. As a parametric study, the effect of the following parameters were investigated. The temperatures at the anode and cathode inlet were changed to investigate the effect of the temperature distribution on the entire cell and to observe the heat pipe effect. As a result of conducted study, it was found that because of the velocity of the methanol is higher than that of oxygen, the heat transfer at the anode side is relatively higher than that of the cathode side. In addition, because of the temperature within the CAC was ~10°C lower than the set point temperature, the flooding condition took place within the CAC which was originated from heat pipe effect.

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Nomenclature

P	Pressure [N/m ²]
T	Temperature [K]
C	Concentration [mol/m ³]
V	Cell Voltage [V]
k	Thermal Conductivity [W/mK]
M	Molecular Weight [kg/mol]
C_p	Heat Capacitance [J/ kg K]
u	Velocity [m/s]
ai_o	Reference exchange current density [A/m ³]
i	Current Density [A/m ²]
j	Volumetric Current Density [A/m ³]
j_{xover}	Crossover Current Density [A/m ³]
D	Diffusion Coefficient [m ² /s]
h	Enthalpy [kJ/mol]
K_c	Reaction Constant for Methanol Oxidation [mol/m ³]
Q_{br}	Source term
n_d	Coefficient of Electro-osmotic Drag
\dot{N}''	Molar Flux [mol/m ² s]
\dot{N}'''	Volumetric Molar Flux, [mol/m ³ s]
S_{trans}	Transport Source Term [mol/m ³ s]
S_u	Source term in continuity equation [N/m ³]
F	Faraday sabiti [C/mol]

R	Universal Gas Constant [J/molK]
a	Activity, unitless
J	Leverett J-Function, unitless
S_{gen}^k	Consumption/Generation Flux of Species k, [mol/m ³ s]
s	Liquid Saturation, unitless
k_H	Henry's Constant, unitless
j_l	Capillary Diffusion Flux of Liquid State [kg/m ² s]
v_{FEC}	Flowing Electrolyte Velocity [m/s]

Greeks Letters

α	Transfer Coefficient
ε	Porosity
ρ	Density [kg/m ³]
σ	Conductivity [S/m]
κ	Permeability [m ²]
η	Overpotential [V]
ϕ	Potential [V]
κ	Electrical Conductance [S/m]
θ_c	Contact Angle [°C]
γ	Advection correction factor
ν	Kinematic Viscosity [m ² /s]
σ	Surface Tension [N/m ²]

Abbreviations

AFC	Anode Fuel Channel
ABL	Anode Backing Layer
ACL	Anode Catalyst Layer
AM	Anode Membrane
FEC	Flowing Electrolyte Channel
CM	Cathode Membrane
CCL	Cathode Catalyst Layer
CBL	Cathode Backing Layer
CAC	Cathode Air Channel
MOR	Methanol Oxidation Reaction
OCV	Open Circuit Voltage
ORR	Oxygen Reduction Reaction
MEA	Membrane Electrode Assembly
FE	Flowing Electrolyte
EOD	Electro-osmotic Drag
MMM	Multiphase Mixture Model
MFM	Multi-Fluid Model

Subscript/Superscript

lg	Two-phase Condition
MeOH	Methanol
O ₂	Oxygen
H ₂ O	Water
ref	Reference Value
s	Solid Phase
e	Electrolyte Phase
l	Liquid phase
g	Gaseous/Vapour State
eff	Effective Value
xover	Crossover
a	Anode
c	Cathode
in	Inlet
out	Outlet
k	Species

fg	phase change
FC	Anode Fuel Channel
ABL	Anode Backing Layer
ACL	Anode Catalyst Layer
AM	Anode Membrane
FEC	Flowing Electrolyte Channel
CM	Cathode Membrane
CCL	Cathode Catalyst Layer
CBL	Cathode Backing Layer
AC	Cathode Air Channel
channel	Channel

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